

TERMS AS AN OBJECT OF STUDY

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Annotation

This article is devoted to the study of terms. It analyzes the scale of the meaning of the word term. In addition, based on the researches of terminologists, the connections and differences between the concepts of terminology and nomenclature were considered. Some scientists in their works emphasize the importance of clearly defining the boundary between terminology and nomenclature concepts.

Keywords: nomenclature, terminological system, determination, terminology, geographical terms.

Introduction

The scope of research on the question of terms is very large, in which various theoretical and practical issues of terminology and terminology are studied in detail. Such issues include the relationship between a term and a word in a universal language, the relationship between a terminological system and a universal language, the formation, development of terms, determination, translation of terms, etc.

In research, the term terminology is used in the following two senses:

1. Terminology is the sum, set of words and combinations of words that represent a special meaning.

2. Terminology is a branch of linguistic science that deals with the study of the laws related to terms, their grammatical structure and their validity in language [1].

A.A. Reformatsky argues that the term will always belong to a specific terminological field, and within that field it will have only one meaning [2]. Hence, terms that represent objects or concepts related to a particular field form terminology in close connection with each other in their meaning, lexical-grammatical structure and other characteristics.

The concept of Nomenclature, which is close to terminology, is very similar to "terms" in terms of its function. The word "nomenclature" comes from Latin and means "to write, to call names". A.D. Khayutin argues that the word in question was first coined by the Botanical scientist Linnaeus, who served him in the creation of a classification of plants [3].

To the connection between terminology and the concepts of nomenclature

A.A. Reformatsky expressed his attitude and opposes the fact that these two concepts are called synonyms. He argues that words that represent a geographical concept, such as "sea", "River", "Mountain", "City", are geographical terms, while words such as "Caspian", "Volga", "Pamir", "Moscow" are geographical nomenclature [4].

The nomenclature usually includes the names of various types of equipment, tooling. V.M. Leychik believes that the nomenclature should include words that serve to designate the same types of objects. In this context, the scientist interprets the nomenclature as an intermediate link between terms and proper names [5].

Some scientists in their works emphasize the importance of clearly defining the boundary between terminology and nomenclature concepts. A.D. Khayutin in turn, considers it desirable to study terminology in opposition to nomenclature [6].

A term referring to an object or reality first defines and describes that object or reality. In nomenclature, however, this is not observed. Their function is limited to naming things and objects. Therefore, "term" is a broad and clear concept in relation to nomenclature, and, given the meaning of the word in a special function, "nomenclature" is a term that serves to designate objects and concepts that are similar to each other.

The term comes from the Latin terminus, the first lexical meaning of which is "check, border" (Larousse, 1046). Its second meaning refers to a special vocabulary that relates to a specific field of science, technology, art, and others. The word "term" entered the Uzbek language in the 40-50s of the 20th century. Prior to this period, the words "profession" and "adjective" were used [7-13].

As we noted above, there is currently no single view in the linguistic literature on the definition of a term, which is considered the main issue of terminology. In our opinion, the only definition of the term that satisfies everyone will not be accepted in the coming years. The reason is that the concept of the term is of interest not only to linguists, but also to specialists in various fields. Each of them approaches

the problem of the term based on their own fields, and this circumstance is ultimately, makes it advisable to decide on the adoption of a general definition of the term. Zero, the term is an object of linguistics from the point of view of the law and norm of language, from the point of view of the expressed concept, from various fields [14-18].

Information about the basic concepts of any science is transmitted to people through a scientific definition. D.P. According to Gorsky, the scientific definition implies the solution of two extremely important tasks. First, to reveal the main features and essence of the subject being described, and, secondly, to show the same object its differences from objects that are similar or close to it [8].

Depending on the definitions given to the term, they all have D.P. It is noticeable that the Gorsky principle was followed differently. In general, the definitions given to the term can be divided into the following types:

- a) definitions based on deep logic;
- b) definitions given by describing the key characters specific to a particular term;
- c) definitions given by placing a term opposite another language unit;
- d) "Working" definitions that are intended to be valid only within the framework of specific research by scientists.

As long as there is no single view in the linguistic literature on the definition of this term, this issue does not lose its relevance. Most of the definitions given to this term fix its characteristics, such as the representation of special objects and concepts, the limitation of performing a special task, providing information about scientific understanding, implying concepts related to a special field, lack of expressiveness and emotionality.

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